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Small and Medium Enterprises, Climate Risks, and Interest Rate Constraints: Implications for Employment in Northern Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) play a pivotal role in employment generation and livelihood sustenance in Northern Nigeria. However, their capacity to create and sustain jobs is increasingly threatened by rising climate risks and persistent interest rate constraints. This study examines the effects of climate-related risks and high borrowing costs on SME employment in Northern Nigeria using firm-level survey data complemented by secondary climate and macroeconomic indicators. Using Poisson and Negative Binomial regression techniques, the study finds that climate risks significantly reduce SME employment, while high interest rates further constrain firms' labour-absorption capacity. The interaction between climate risk exposure and interest rate constraints reveals a compounding effect, intensifying employment losses among SMEs facing both environmental and financial stress. The findings underscore SMEs' vulnerability to overlapping structural challenges and highlight the need for integrated policy interventions across climate, finance, and employment. The study contributes to the literature by providing region-specific empirical evidence and offering policy-relevant insights to promote SME resilience, inclusive employment, and sustainable development in Northern Nigeria.

Keywords: Small and Medium Enterprises; Climate Risk; Interest Rates; Employment; Northern Nigeria; Financial Constraints; Sustainable Development

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) are widely acknowledged as the backbone of developing economies, owing to their critical roles in employment generation, income creation, and poverty reduction (Musa et al., 2023). In Nigeria, SMEs dominate the business landscape and constitute a significant source of livelihood, particularly in regions where large-scale industrial activities are limited (Ahmed et al., 2024). Empirical evidence indicates that SMEs account for more than 80 per cent of employment and over 40 per cent of national output, underscoring their importance to inclusive economic growth (SMEDAN & National Bureau of Statistics [NBS], 2022; Muhammed et al., 2025). In Northern Nigeria, where formal employment opportunities remain scarce and economic activities are largely informal and agriculture-linked, SMEs serve as a vital mechanism for absorbing labour and sustaining household

incomes (Magaji et al., 2024). However, SMEs' capacity to fulfil this role is increasingly threatened by escalating climate risks and persistent interest rate constraints (Musa & Magaji, 2024).

Climate change has emerged as one of the most significant structural challenges confronting SMEs globally, with disproportionate effects in climate-sensitive regions such as Northern Nigeria. The region is characterised by semi-arid ecological conditions, high dependence on rain-fed agriculture, and limited adaptive infrastructure, making SMEs particularly vulnerable to climate-induced shocks (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change [IPCC], 2022). Extreme weather events—including floods, droughts, heat stress, and desertification—have intensified in frequency and severity, disrupting production cycles, damaging physical assets, and destabilising supply chains (World Bank, 2021). For SMEs operating in agriculture, agro-processing, trade, and allied services, climate variability directly affects raw material availability, operating costs, and market access, with adverse consequences for business continuity and labour demand.

The devastating floods experienced across Nigeria in 2022 vividly illustrate the employment risks associated with climate shocks. The floods displaced millions of people, destroyed farmlands, damaged commercial infrastructure, and forced the temporary or permanent closure of thousands of micro and small enterprises (NBS, 2023). In Northern Nigeria, where SMEs often lack insurance coverage and emergency buffers, such climate events translate rapidly into layoffs, reduced working hours, and income losses. Studies have shown that climate-related business disruptions disproportionately affect youth and women, who are heavily concentrated in informal and micro-enterprise employment (African Development Bank [AfDB], 2022). Consequently, climate risks pose not only environmental and economic challenges but also serious concerns for labour markets and social stability.

Alongside climate risks, financial constraints—particularly high and volatile interest rates—constitute a significant barrier to SME growth and employment creation in Nigeria (Igwe et al., 2021; Magaji & Aliyu, 2007). Monetary policy tightening, inflationary pressures, and structural inefficiencies in the financial sector have contributed to persistently high lending rates, making access to affordable credit difficult for SMEs (Central Bank of Nigeria [CBN], 2023; Musa et al., 2022). High interest rates raise the cost of capital, discourage long-term investment, and limit SMEs' ability to expand operations or adopt productivity-enhancing technologies (Beck & Demirgüç-Kunt, 2006; Magaji et al., 2023). In Northern Nigeria, these constraints are further compounded by weak financial inclusion, limited collateral availability, and heightened perceptions of credit risk by formal lenders.

Empirical studies consistently demonstrate a negative relationship between high interest rates and SME performance in Nigeria. For instance, Ibrahim (2024) finds that elevated borrowing costs significantly reduce SMEs' profitability, investment capacity, and employment growth. When access to credit is constrained, SMEs often resort to cost-cutting strategies, such as downsizing labour, freezing recruitment, or shifting to precarious employment arrangements. This has important implications for regional employment outcomes, particularly in Northern Nigeria, where SMEs represent the primary source of non-farm jobs.

Importantly, climate risks and interest rate constraints do not operate in isolation; instead, they interact, compounding SMEs' vulnerability and amplifying employment losses. Climate shocks can weaken SMEs' financial positions, increase default risks and further limit access to credit. At the same time, high interest rates restrict firms' capacity to invest in climate adaptation and resilience measures (Skouloudis et al., 2023). This vicious cycle undermines business sustainability and constrains SMEs' ability to maintain stable employment levels. From a development perspective, this interaction poses a significant threat to poverty reduction, youth employment, and economic stability in Northern Nigeria (Abeke et al., 2025).

Despite the growing relevance of these challenges, existing empirical literature in Nigeria has broadly examined climate change, SME financing, and employment outcomes as separate issues. There remains a notable gap in integrated analyses that simultaneously assess climate risks and interest rate constraints and their combined implications for SME-driven employment, particularly at the regional level. Addressing this gap is essential for informing coherent policy responses that align climate adaptation strategies with inclusive financial systems and employment objectives.

Against this backdrop, this study examines the interconnections between SMEs, climate risks, and interest rate constraints, with specific emphasis on their implications for employment in Northern Nigeria. By situating SME performance within both environmental and financial contexts, the study contributes to a more holistic understanding of the structural challenges facing SMEs. It highlights policy pathways to enhance enterprise resilience, sustain employment, and promote inclusive regional development.

Literature Review

2.1 Conceptual Definitions

2.1.1. Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs)

Small and Medium Enterprises are commonly defined based on criteria such as number of employees, asset base, and annual turnover, though these thresholds vary across countries and institutions. In Nigeria, SMEs are officially defined by the *Small and Medium Enterprises Development Agency of Nigeria* (SMEDAN) as enterprises employing fewer than 200 persons with assets not exceeding ₦500 million, excluding land and buildings (SMEDAN & NBS, 2022). SMEs play a critical role in employment generation, innovation, and regional economic development, particularly in developing economies where large-scale industries are limited (Beck & Demirgüç-Kunt, 2006; Magaji & Saleh, 2010; Magaji et al., 2015). In Northern Nigeria, SMEs are predominantly micro and small enterprises operating in agriculture, agro-processing, trading, transportation, and informal services, making them highly sensitive to environmental and financial shocks (Ismail et al., 2025).

2.1.2 Climate Risks

Climate risks refer to the potential adverse effects arising from climate variability and climate change, including extreme weather events such as floods, droughts, heat waves, desertification, and irregular rainfall patterns (Abubakar et al., 2025). These risks affect economic systems by damaging physical assets, disrupting production processes, destabilising supply chains, and increasing operational uncertainty (Ibrahim et al., 2025). For SMEs, climate risks are particularly severe due to limited financial buffers, weak insurance coverage, and low adaptive capacity (World Bank, 2021). In Northern Nigeria, climate risks are intensified by ecological fragility, dependence on rain-fed agriculture, and inadequate infrastructure, which expose SMEs to frequent climate-induced business disruptions.

2.1.3 Interest Rate Constraints

Interest rate constraints refer to the limitations on firms' access to credit arising from high, volatile, or unpredictable lending rates. High interest rates increase the cost of borrowing, reduce investment incentives, and constrain business expansion, especially for SMEs that rely heavily on external financing (CBN, 2023). In Nigeria, structural issues within the financial sector, inflationary pressures, and tight monetary policy have contributed to persistently high lending rates, disproportionately affecting SMEs (Ibrahim, 2024). For SMEs in Northern Nigeria, interest rate constraints are compounded by low financial inclusion, inadequate collateral, and perceived regional risk, further limiting access to affordable credit.

2.1.4 Employment

Employment refers to the engagement of labour in productive economic activities that generate income and livelihoods (Adekoya et al., 2025). SMEs are widely recognised as the most significant contributors to employment in Nigeria, particularly informal and non-farm employment in rural and semi-urban areas (NBS, 2023). Employment generated by SMEs is often flexible but vulnerable, making it highly sensitive to external shocks such as climate events and financial constraints. When SMEs face operational stress, employment outcomes are typically the first adjustment mechanism, with downsizing, reduced working hours, or informalization of labour.

2.2 Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on three complementary theoretical perspectives: Vulnerability Theory, Financial Constraint Theory, and Employment Adjustment Theory.

Vulnerability Theory

Vulnerability Theory emphasises the exposure, sensitivity, and adaptive capacity of economic agents to external shocks (Adger, 2006). Applied to SMEs, the theory suggests that enterprises with limited resources, weak institutional support, and high dependence on environmental conditions are more vulnerable to climate risks. SMEs in Northern Nigeria exhibit high exposure and sensitivity to climate variability due to their reliance on agriculture-related activities and limited access to adaptive technologies. Climate shocks reduce productivity and revenues, increasing the likelihood of business failure and employment losses.

Financial Constraint Theory

Financial Constraint Theory posits that imperfections in credit markets limit firms' access to external finance, thereby constraining investment, growth, and employment (Stiglitz & Weiss, 1981). SMEs are particularly affected by credit rationing due to information asymmetry, lack of collateral, and higher perceived risk. In the Nigerian context, high interest rates exacerbate financial constraints, reducing SMEs' ability to invest in climate adaptation measures, expand operations, or sustain employment during economic or environmental shocks. This theory provides a strong foundation for analysing how interest rate constraints interact with climate risks to influence SME performance and employment outcomes.

Employment Adjustment Theory

Employment Adjustment Theory suggests that firms respond to adverse economic conditions by adjusting labour inputs before other factors of production, given labour's relative flexibility (Hamermesh, 1993). For SMEs, employment adjustments often take the form of layoffs, reduced working hours, or reliance on unpaid family labour. When SMEs face declining revenues due to climate shocks or rising borrowing costs, employment becomes a key adjustment variable. This framework helps explain why climate risks and interest rate constraints have direct, immediate implications for employment in SME-dominated economies such as Northern Nigeria.

2.3 Empirical Evidence

Empirical studies provide substantial evidence on the relationship between SMEs, climate risks, interest rates, and employment, though integrated analyses remain limited.

Globally, studies have shown that climate change adversely affects SME productivity, profitability, and survival rates. Skouloudis et al. (2023) find that SMEs exposed to climate risks experience higher operational disruptions and reduced employment stability, particularly in developing economies with weak institutional support. Similarly, the World Bank (2021) reports that climate shocks disproportionately affect small firms, leading to job losses and increased labour informality.

In the African context, empirical evidence indicates that climate variability significantly undermines SME performance and employment, especially in agriculture-dependent regions. AfDB (2022) documents that droughts and floods reduce SME output and labour demand, with youth and women being the most affected. Studies on Nigeria reveal that climate-induced events, such as floods and desertification, disrupt SME activities, increase business closures, and exacerbate unemployment in northern regions (NBS, 2023). El-Yaqub, Ismail and Eke (2024) analyze the impact of commercial bank credit on small and medium scale enterprise in Nigeria: 1992 to 2022 using Autoregressive Distributed Lag model (ARDL). The stationarity results showed that SMEs profit (SMEP) and Lending rate (LENR) were integrated at levels $I(0)$ while commercial bank credit to SMEs (CLSME) and money supply (TMS) were stationary after the first different. The result of the ARDL Bound test showed that long-run relationships are thus evident between the variables. Furthermore, the result demonstrates that the adjustment mechanism (ECMt-1) is statistically significant and has the necessary sign (negative). Showing that a short-term shock will eventually be brought to equilibrium at an average pace of 95% annually. The ARDL results showed that CLSME has a negative and a positive significant impact on SMEP in the short run and the long run, respectively. LENR has a positive significant and insignificant impact on SMEP in the short run and long run, respectively. Finally, TMS has a positive and a negative significant impact on SMEP in short run and the long run, respectively. The study concluded that commercial bank credit has impact on small and medium scale enterprise (SMEs) in Nigeria. Hence, the study recommended that commercial

banks should prioritize lending to small and medium scale in Nigeria with a view to achieve rapid growth among SMEs in Nigeria, and government through monetary policy authority should reduce lending rate that will be profitable to small and medium enterprise with intention for business expansion and creation of jobs in the country.

Bariki, Muhammad and Ismail (2025) examine the challenges posed by tax policies on the survival of Small and Medium-Scale Enterprises (SMEs) in Nigeria, focusing on the Gwagwalada Area Council, Abuja. Using a survey design and collecting data from 220 SME owners/managers, the research employed multiple linear regression to analyze the impact of four key policy factors: Tax Burden, Compliance Cost, Tax Incentives, and Regulatory Complexity, on SME survival. The findings indicated that the tax environment significantly threatens SME viability, with high Regulatory Complexity ($\beta=-0.45$, $p=0.000$) emerging as the strongest negative predictor of survival, closely followed by the overall Tax Burden ($\beta=-0.38$, $p=0.000$). High Compliance Costs ($\beta=-0.25$, $p=0.002$) also significantly reduced business survival. Conversely, the availability and effectiveness of Tax Incentives had a modest positive impact ($\beta=0.15$, $p=0.034$). The model, which was highly significant ($R^2=0.68$), strongly supports the conclusion that the current tax regime characterized by complexity, high cost, and burden acts as a major deterrent to SME growth and sustainability. The study recommends urgent tax policy reforms to streamline administration, reduce the multiple taxation burden, and enhance the accessibility of targeted incentives to foster a more business friendly ecosystem.

Regarding financial constraints, extensive literature confirms that high interest rates negatively affect SME growth and employment. Beck and Demirgüç-Kunt (2006) demonstrate that limited access to affordable finance constrains SMEs' investment capacity and job creation. In Nigeria, Ibrahim (2024) finds a significant negative relationship between lending rates and SME performance, with higher interest rates leading to reduced employment generation. Similarly, CBN (2023) reports that SMEs facing high borrowing costs are less likely to expand or sustain their workforce.

Few studies have examined the combined effects of climate risks and financial constraints on SMEs. However, emerging evidence suggests that climate shocks worsen SMEs' creditworthiness, while financial constraints limit their ability to adapt to climate risks, creating a reinforcing cycle of vulnerability (World Bank, 2021; Skouloudis et al., 2023). This interaction has critical implications for employment, particularly in regions such as Northern Nigeria, where SMEs dominate labour markets.

Overall, the empirical literature highlights the centrality of SMEs in employment generation, the disruptive effects of climate risks, and the constraining role of high interest rates. However, there remains a clear gap in region-specific, integrated studies that examine how climate risks and interest rate constraints jointly affect SME-driven employment in Northern Nigeria. This study seeks to fill this gap by providing a comprehensive and context-sensitive analysis.

METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

This study adopts a quantitative research design using a cross-sectional analytical approach to examine the effects of climate risks and interest rate constraints on employment outcomes among Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Northern Nigeria. A quantitative design is appropriate because it enables the systematic measurement of relationships among variables and supports statistical inference regarding the magnitude and direction of effects (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). The study integrates firm-level survey data with secondary climate and macroeconomic indicators to provide a comprehensive assessment of environmental and financial constraints affecting SME employment.

3.2 Study Area

The study focuses on Northern Nigeria, comprising the North-East, North-West, and North-Central geopolitical zones. This region is characterised by high SME concentration, climate vulnerability, and elevated unemployment rates compared with southern Nigeria (NBS, 2023). Northern Nigeria experiences recurrent droughts, floods, desertification, and temperature extremes, which disproportionately affect SME-dominated sectors such as agriculture, agro-processing, trade, and services

(World Bank, 2021). The region is therefore suitable for analysing the intersection of climate risks, financial constraints, and employment outcomes.

3.3 Population of the Study

The target population consists of registered and unregistered SMEs operating across selected states in Northern Nigeria. Consistent with SMEDAN classification, SMEs include enterprises employing fewer than 200 workers and operating with limited capital intensity (SMEDAN & NBS, 2022). The study includes SMEs from agriculture, manufacturing, trade, and service sectors, given their relevance to regional employment generation. Micro-enterprises with no hired labour were excluded to ensure meaningful employment analysis.

3.4 Sampling Technique and Sample Size

A multi-stage sampling technique was employed. First, three states were purposively selected from each of the three northern geopolitical zones based on SME density and climate exposure. Second, local government areas (LGAs) with high SME activity were randomly selected within each state. Third, SMEs were selected using stratified random sampling to ensure sectoral representation.

The sample size was determined using Yamane's (1967) formula for finite populations:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where n is the sample size, N is the estimated population of SMEs, and e is the level of precision (5%). This resulted in a minimum sample size of approximately 400 SMEs, consistent with similar empirical studies of SMEs in developing economies (Beck & Demirgüç-Kunt, 2006).

3.5 Data Sources and Data Collection

The study relies on both primary and secondary data sources.

Primary data were collected through a structured questionnaire administered to SME owners or managers. The questionnaire captured information on employment levels, climate-related business disruptions, access to finance, borrowing costs, and firm characteristics. To enhance reliability, the instrument was pre-tested, and necessary refinements were made prior to full deployment.

Secondary data on climate variables (rainfall variability, temperature anomalies, and flood incidence) were obtained from the Nigerian Meteorological Agency (NiMet) and World Bank climate databases. Interest rate data and macroeconomic indicators were sourced from the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) Statistical Bulletin.

3.6 Measurement of Variables

Dependent Variable

Employment is measured as the total number of paid employees an SME had at the time of the survey. This measure is widely used in SME and labour market studies (Hamermesh, 1993).

Independent Variables

Climate risk is captured using a Climate Risk Index, constructed from self-reported exposure to floods, droughts, extreme heat, and rainfall variability, complemented by state-level objective climate data (IPCC, 2022).

The interest rate constraint is measured using the effective lending rate faced by SMEs and a binary indicator of whether high interest rates constrained access to credit during the previous 12 months.

Control Variables

Control variables include firm age, firm size, sector of operation, owner's education level, access to insurance, and location (urban/rural), consistent with prior SME performance literature (Beck & Demirgüç-Kunt, 2006).

3.7 Model Specification

To estimate the impact of climate risks and interest rate constraints on SME employment, the study specifies the following econometric model:

$$EMP_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 CR_i + \beta_2 IR_i + \beta_3 X_i + \varepsilon_i$$

Where:

EMP_i = employment level of SME i

CR_i = climate risk exposure index

IR_i = interest rate constraint

X_i = vector of control variables

ε_i = error term

Given the count nature of employment data, the study employs Poisson and Negative Binomial regression models, with robustness checks using Ordinary Least Squares (OLS). Negative Binomial regression is preferred where over-dispersion is detected (Cameron & Trivedi, 2013).

3.8 Estimation Technique

The estimation follows a stepwise approach. Descriptive statistics are first used to summarise key variables and identify patterns. Correlation analysis is conducted to assess multicollinearity among the variables. Regression analyses are then performed to estimate the effects of climate risks and interest rate constraints on employment. Robust standard errors are applied to correct for heteroskedasticity.

3.9 Ethical Considerations

Ethical standards were strictly observed throughout the research process. Participation was voluntary, and informed consent was obtained from all respondents. Confidentiality of responses was ensured, and no personal identifiers were collected. The study complies with standard ethical guidelines for social science research (Creswell & Creswell, 2018).

3.10 Limitations of the Methodology

The study acknowledges limitations, including reliance on cross-sectional data, which restricts causal inference, and potential response bias arising from self-reported data. However, triangulation with secondary climate and macroeconomic data enhances the robustness of findings.

4.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Descriptive Statistics

Table 1 presents the descriptive statistics of the key variables used in the analysis. On average, SMEs in Northern Nigeria employ approximately six workers, reflecting the dominance of micro and small enterprises. Climate risk exposure shows considerable variation, indicating uneven vulnerability across states and sectors. Interest rates faced by SMEs are relatively high, reinforcing concerns about credit affordability.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics of Key Variables

Variable	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
Employment (number of workers)	6.12	4.85	1	28
Climate Risk Index	0.57	0.21	0.12	0.94
Interest Rate (%)	27.4	6.3	15.0	38.0
Firm Age (years)	8.6	5.2	1	30
Firm Size (log assets)	12.9	1.8	9.4	17.6

The descriptive results suggest that SMEs operate with small workforces and face both high climate exposure and costly credit, conditions likely to affect employment decisions.

4.2 Correlation Analysis

Table 2 reports the pairwise correlation coefficients. Employment is negatively correlated with climate risk and interest rates, suggesting that higher environmental and financial stress may reduce labour

absorption. The absence of excessively high correlation values indicates that multicollinearity is not a concern.

Table 2: Correlation Matrix

Variable	Employment	Climate Risk	Interest Rate
Employment	1.00		
Climate Risk	-0.42	1.00	
Interest Rate	-0.36	0.19	1.00

4.3 Regression Results

Given the count nature of the employment variable, Poisson regression was first estimated, followed by Negative Binomial regression due to evidence of over-dispersion. The estimated baseline model is specified as:

$$\ln(EMP_i) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 CR_i + \beta_2 IR_i + \beta_3 X_i + \varepsilon_i$$

where

EMP_i = employment level of SME i

CR_i = climate risk exposure

IR_i = interest rate constraint

X_i = vector of control variables

4.4 Poisson and Negative Binomial Estimates

Table 3: Regression Results – Determinants of SME Employment

Variables	Poisson	Negative Binomial	
Climate Risk Index	-0.614*** (0.102)	-0.572*** (0.118)	
Interest Rate	-0.028** (0.013)	-0.031** (0.014)	
Firm Age	0.019* (0.011)	0.021* (0.012)	
Firm Size	0.246*** (0.054)	0.231*** (0.058)	
Urban Location	0.188** (0.081)	0.172** (0.087)	
Constant	1.412***	1.366***	
Observations	400	400	
Log-Likelihood	-912.4	-781.6	
Over-dispersion (α)	—	0.84***	
***p < 0.01,		**p < 0.05,	*p < 0.10

(Standard errors in parentheses)

4.5 DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

The regression results provide strong evidence that climate risks and interest rate constraints significantly reduce SME employment in Northern Nigeria.

The coefficient of the Climate Risk Index is negative and statistically significant across all model specifications. In the Negative Binomial model, a one-unit increase in climate risk exposure reduces expected employment by approximately 57 per cent, holding other factors constant. This finding aligns with Vulnerability Theory, which posits that enterprises with limited adaptive capacity experience disproportionate losses when exposed to environmental shocks (Adger, 2006). Climate-related disruptions, such as floods, droughts, and extreme heat, disrupt production continuity and force SMEs to downsize their workforce.

Similarly, the interest rate variable shows a negative and significant effect on employment. Higher borrowing costs constrain SMEs' access to working capital and limit their ability to expand or even maintain current employment levels. This result supports Financial Constraint Theory (Stiglitz & Weiss, 1981) and is consistent with Nigerian evidence that high lending rates suppress SME growth and labour demand (Ibrahim, 2024).

Among the control variables, firm size and firm age exhibit positive and significant effects on employment, suggesting that larger and more established SMEs are better positioned to absorb shocks and sustain labour. Urban-based SMEs also employ more workers than their rural counterparts, reflecting better access to markets, infrastructure, and finance.

The significance of the over-dispersion parameter confirms that the Negative Binomial model is more appropriate than Poisson estimation, reinforcing the robustness of the findings.

4.6 Combined Effects of Climate Risk and Interest Rates

To capture interaction effects, an extended model was estimated:

$$\ln(EMP_i) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 CR_i + \beta_2 IR_i + \beta_3 (CR_i \times IR_i) + \beta_4 X_i + \varepsilon_i$$

Table 4: Interaction Effects of Climate Risk and Interest Rates

Variable	Negative Binomial
Climate Risk	-0.481***
Interest Rate	-0.024**
Climate Risk × Interest Rate	-0.017**
Controls	Included
Observations	400

The negative and significant interaction term indicates that the employment-reducing effect of climate risks is amplified under high interest rate conditions. This suggests that SMEs facing climate shocks are less able to respond when borrowing costs are high, limiting investment in recovery or adaptation and accelerating employment losses.

4.7 Implications

The results demonstrate that environmental vulnerability and financial constraints jointly undermine SME-driven employment in Northern Nigeria. Climate change not only disrupts production but also weakens firms' financial standing, while high interest rates restrict access to adaptation finance. Together, these forces create a reinforcing cycle of vulnerability that threatens inclusive employment and regional economic stability.

Summary of Key Findings

- i. Climate risks significantly reduce SME employment
- ii. High interest rates constrain labour demand
- iii. Larger and older firms are more resilient
- iv. Climate risks and interest rates jointly intensify employment losses

CONCLUSION

This study examined the implications of climate risks and interest rate constraints for employment generation among Small and Medium Enterprises in Northern Nigeria. Drawing on firm-level data and robust econometric techniques, the findings provide compelling evidence that both climate-related shocks and high borrowing costs significantly undermine SMEs' capacity to sustain and expand employment. Climate risks—manifesting through floods, droughts, and temperature extremes—disrupt production processes, damage business assets, and weaken revenue streams, compelling SMEs to adjust by reducing labour demand. At the same time, elevated interest rates increase the cost of capital, restrict access to

finance, and limit SMEs' ability to invest in growth or climate adaptation, thereby constraining job creation.

Notably, the study demonstrates that climate risks and interest rate constraints interact in a reinforcing manner. SMEs exposed to high climate risk face more severe employment losses when credit conditions are tight, indicating that financial constraints weaken firms' adaptive capacity. This interaction highlights a critical vulnerability channel through which environmental and macroeconomic factors jointly affect labour markets in SME-dominated economies. The findings further show that larger and more established firms are relatively more resilient, suggesting that firm capacity and access to resources play an important role in mitigating employment losses.

Overall, the study contributes to the empirical literature by integrating environmental and financial dimensions into the analysis of SME employment outcomes, with a specific focus on Northern Nigeria. The results underscore the urgency of coordinated policy responses that address both climate vulnerability and financial constraints in order to safeguard SME-driven employment and promote inclusive regional development.

Policy Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following policy recommendations are proposed:

1. **Climate-Responsive SME Support Policies:** Government and development agencies should design and implement climate-responsive SME support programs, including early warning systems, climate information services, and technical assistance, to reduce SMEs' exposure and sensitivity to climate risks. Strengthening SMEs' adaptive capacity will help stabilise production and protect employment during climate shocks.
2. **Concessional and Targeted SME Financing:** There is a need to expand access to affordable credit for SMEs through concessional lending schemes, interest rate subsidies, and credit guarantee programs, particularly for enterprises operating in climate-vulnerable regions. Lower borrowing costs would enhance SMEs' investment capacity and support employment retention and expansion.
3. **Integration of Climate Finance and SME Development:** Policymakers should integrate climate finance mechanisms—such as green credit lines and adaptation funds—into SME development strategies. Facilitating access to climate-adaptation financing will enable SMEs to invest in resilient technologies and infrastructure, reducing the employment impacts of climate shocks.
4. **Strengthening Financial Inclusion in Northern Nigeria:** Efforts to deepen financial inclusion, including expanding microfinance institutions, digital financial services, and tailored SME banking products, are essential to reducing regional credit constraints. Improved access to finance would enhance SMEs' resilience and their potential to generate employment.
5. **Employment-Focused SME Resilience Programs:** Employment protection measures, such as wage support schemes, skills upgrading, and enterprise formalisation incentives, should be embedded within SME resilience frameworks. Such measures would help cushion workers against job losses during periods of environmental and financial stress.
6. **Data and Monitoring for Evidence-Based Policy:** Regular collection of firm-level data on climate exposure, financing conditions, and employment outcomes is crucial for monitoring SME vulnerability and evaluating the effectiveness of policies. Strengthening data systems will support evidence-based policymaking and targeted interventions.

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